

Stylometric Stratification of Pali Sutta Texts: A Corpus-Wide Study Using Binary Classification

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Abstract

What if earliest Buddhist teaching looked quite different from later scholastic systematization? This study applies machine learning stylometry to the Pali Canon, training a classifier on philologically established early versus late texts (AUC 0.859 segments, 0.973 blocks). The model uses character n-grams alone and has no access to word meaning. Yet high-scoring passages show more than 5 higher parallel attestation; late markers are absent; filtered results isolate suttas scholarship considers core. This convergence of a meaning-blind model with independent criteria suggests genuine chronological signal. Terminological patterns point toward a pragmatic, pre-systematic archaic stratum.

Keywords: *Pali Canon, stylometry, Early Buddhist Texts, textual stratification, machine learning, computational philology*

1. Introduction

The question of chronological stratification within the Pali Canon has occupied scholars since Rhys Davids and Oldenberg.¹ There is broad consensus that certain texts—notably the Atthakavagga and Parayanavagga of the Sutta Nipata—represent an archaic stratum.² Dating individual suttas or passages, however, remains contentious. Traditional criteria include linguistic archaism, metrical patterns, doctrinal simplicity, and absence of scholastic elaboration.³ But these are often applied impressionistically, and different scholars weigh them differently.

1 T. W. Rhys Davids, *Buddhist India* (London: T. Fisher Unwin, 1903); H. Oldenberg, *Buddha: His Life, His Doctrine, His Order*, trans. W. Hoey (London: Williams and Norgate, 1912).

2 K. R. Norman, *Pali Literature* (Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz, 1983); L. O. Gomez, “Proto-Madhyamika in the Pali Canon,” *Philosophy East and West* 26, no. 2 (1976): 137–165; A. Wynne, “The Historical Authenticity of Early Buddhist Literature,” *Vienna Journal of South Asian Studies* 49 (2005): 35–70; Bhikkhu Sujato and Bhikkhu Brahmali, *The Authenticity of the Early Buddhist Texts* (Chroniker Press, 2015).

Computational stylometry offers a potential complement. By extracting quantifiable features from texts and training classifiers on established exemplars, we can identify patterns that might escape unaided reading. The approach has proven fruitful for authorship attribution⁴ and has been applied to Sanskrit epic literature.⁵ Applications to Pali remain scarce. Analayo compared Agama parallels without computational methods;⁶ recent corpus-linguistic work has focused on lexical frequency rather than classification. To my knowledge, no previous study has used the philologically established early core as supervised training data to search systematically for stylistically similar passages across the entire canon.

The present study trains a logistic regression classifier on philologically established early-stratum texts (Sutta Nipata IV–V and related archaic materials: Snp 1.3, 1.12, 3.6, 3.11) against demonstrably late compositions (Buddhavamsa, Petavatthu, Vimanavatthu). Cross-validated AUC reached 0.859 on single segments; grouping into five-segment blocks raised this to 0.973.

Applied to the entire Pali sutta canon, the study addresses: Can a classifier trained on early/late exemplars generalize with reasonable accuracy? Do the nikayas show systematic differences in early-style prevalence? Does the model distinguish editorial frames from doctrinal cores? Do high-scoring passages share features associated with early teaching? Do they find attestation in parallel traditions?

Four independent validation approaches were applied. First, the filtered set was tested for late markers—as cosmological elaboration, *mahapurisalakkhana* lists, *cakkavatti* mythology, names of previous Buddhas, stupa veneration—and these appear effectively absent (zero or near-zero occurrences). Second, cross-tradition parallel analysis using SuttaCentral’s parallels database reveals that high-scoring passages are attested in Chinese Āgamas, Sanskrit manuscripts, and Gāndhārī fragments at rates more than 5 higher than low-scoring passages (Spearman $r = 0.23\text{--}0.36$, $p < 1e-10$; Cohen’s $h = 1.32$). Third, permutation testing confirms the discrimination is genuine ($p < 0.001$). Fourth, n-gram sensitivity analysis shows cross-validated AUC decreased modestly from 0.859 to 0.838, confirming that the chronological signal is robust across feature configurations.

3 H. Nakamura, *Indian Buddhism: A Survey with Bibliographical Notes* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1980).

4 E. Stamatatos, “A Survey of Modern Authorship Attribution Methods,” *JASIST* 60, no. 3 (2009): 538–556.

5 L. M. Fosse, “Stylometry and the Mahabharata,” *Literary and Linguistic Computing* 26, no. 1 (2011): 59–77.

6 Analayo, *A Comparative Study of the Majjhima-nikaya* (Taipei: Dharma Drum, 2011).

If the model captured noise or circular artifacts, this convergence would not occur. Notably, a meaning-blind algorithm independently identifies material that (a) spread across traditions before sectarian splits, (b) lacks markers of late composition, and (c) contains what scholars recognize as core teaching. This triple convergence constitutes the study's primary validation.

The analysis reveals terminological patterns with potential implications. Individual elements score higher than systematic formulas: path factors individually ($P = 0.45\text{--}0.88$) outscore "Noble Eightfold Path" ($P = 0.41$); truth content outscores "Four Noble Truths" ($P = 0.48$). The model distinguishes three registers of *sammadithi*: direct seeing ($P = 0.99$), ethical guarantee ($P = 0.98$), and doctrinal catechism ($P = 0.22$). A bimodal distribution appears in brahmavihara vocabulary: *metta* and *upekkha* cluster early ($P > 0.95$), while *karuna* and *mudita* score much lower ($P < 0.11$). This might suggest—though it certainly does not prove—that systematic packaging is a later development.

Perhaps most striking is the *tilakkhana* pattern. For *anicca* and *dukkha*, ontological formulations score higher than process descriptions. For *anatta* alone, this reverses: "do not regard as self" (*attato samanupassati*, $P = 0.96$) scores much higher than "X is non-self" ($P = 0.35\text{--}0.73$). If genuine, *anatta* may have originally functioned as practical instruction—"stop regarding these things as yourself"—rather than metaphysical claim.

The filtered corpus isolates passages traditional Buddhology considers central: the Oghatharana Sutta's "non-establishment" teaching, the Culamalunkya Sutta's refusal of metaphysical speculation, phenomenological jhana descriptions.

The broader aim: if passages identified as stylistically early turn out to share a coherent doctrinal profile, that profile becomes the strongest candidate for the original nucleus of Buddhist teaching. No method can prove what the historical Buddha said. But convergent evidence from independent criteria can constrain the space of plausible reconstructions.

All findings are preliminary. The training corpus is small, stylistic similarity does not prove chronological priority, and the method has limitations. What stylometry offers is not definitive dating but testable hypotheses for philological investigation.

2. Methods

Data Selection

Training corpora were constructed from digital Pali texts.⁷ The selection of early and late cores follows mainstream philological assessments rather than ad hoc judgments.

Rationale for the early core. The Atthakavagga and Parayanavagga of the Sutta Nipata (chapters IV-V) are widely regarded as among the oldest preserved Buddhist texts on multiple independent grounds: (a) archaic Vedic-style meters absent elsewhere in the canon; (b) linguistic features predating standardized Pali; (c) doctrinal emphasis on individual wanderers rather than organized sangha; (d) minimal systematization and enumeration; (e) independent attestation in Chinese translation (Arthapada/Yizujing T198, c. 250 CE, from a pre-Pali Indic recension),⁸ Gandhari fragments (1st c. BCE - 3rd c. CE),⁹ and Asoka's Bhabru Edict (c. 260 BCE), which recommends the Munigatha (= Snp 1.12) and the Moneyya-sute (= Snp 3.11 Nalaka).¹⁰ I supplemented Snp IV-V with four additional Sutta Nipata texts: Snp 1.3 (Khaggavisana), attested in Gandhari manuscripts and Sanskrit parallels in the Mahavastu;¹¹ Snp 1.12 (Muni) and Snp 3.11 (Nalaka), both referenced in the Bhabru Edict; and Snp 3.6 (Sabhiya), which has a Mahavastu parallel¹² and exhibits archaic stylistic features consistent with the Parayanavagga question-answer format. Ablation tests confirm that Snp IV-V alone yields even slightly higher performance, supplementary suttas was included to enrich the training corpus. Future work could explore alternative corpus configurations.

Rationale for the late core. As contrastive late core I chose texts that even conservative scholarship treats as relatively late. The Buddhavamsa, Petavatthu, and

7 SuttaCentral, bilara-data repository, 2024, <https://github.com/suttacentral/bilara-data>.

8 Seongryong Lee, *Pre-institutional Buddhist Traditions in the Arthapada: A Comparative Study and Complete Annotated Translation of Its Chinese Translation Yizujing (義足經), Derived from an Indic Recension, and Its Pāli Recension Atthakavagga* (PhD dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles, 2024).

9 Harry Falk, "The 'Split' Collection of Kharoṣṭhī Texts," *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University* 14 (2011): 13–23.

10 Norman, *Pali Literature*; Wynne, "Historical Authenticity."

11 R. Salomon, *Ancient Buddhist Scrolls from Gandhara: The British Library Kharosthi Fragments* (Seattle: University of Washington Press, 1999).

12 Bryan G. Levman, "Language Theory, Phonology and Etymology in Buddhism and their Relationship to Brahmanism," *Buddhist Studies Review* 34, no. 1 (2017): 25–51.

Vimanavatthu are dated to the 1st-2nd century BCE on multiple grounds: (a) elaborate cosmological frameworks absent from earlier strata; (b) developed karma-vipaka narratives with heavenly rebirth emphasis; (c) stylistic features consistent with late Khuddaka composition; (d) no parallels, suggesting post-sectarian composition.¹³ These texts share no direct borrowing relationship with the Sutta Nipata early core, avoiding circularity.

Table 1. Training Corpus Summary

Category	Sources	Segments
Early Core (verse)	Sn̐ IV-V, Sn̐ 1.3, 1.12, 3.6, 3.11	2,406
Late Core (verse)	Buddhavamsa, Petavatthu, Vimanavatthu	11,212
Total Training		13,618

The full test corpus comprised the entire Pali sutta collection: 240,353 segments across 5,725 suttas in the five nikayas (DN: 16,212; MN: 26,775; SN: 38,997; AN: 38,047; KN: 120,322). The Niddesa texts (Mahaniddesa, Culaniddesa) were excluded from analysis, as these canonical commentaries extensively quote Sn̐ IV-V verbatim, which would artificially inflate early-style detection.

Feature Extraction

Texts were segmented into meaningful units corresponding to the bilara segment structure (verses, short prose passages) and preprocessed to remove punctuation while preserving Pali diacritics. Feature extraction employed: (a) character n-grams (3-5), capturing morphological patterns without requiring lemmatization; (b) TF-IDF weighting to normalize for segment length; (c) lexical features including type-token ratio and average word length. The feature matrix comprised 2,000 dimensions after frequency thresholding (minimum document frequency = 2).

Character n-grams inevitably capture some doctrinally loaded vocabulary (e.g., *paccay-*, *bhav-*). This is both a strength—such terms genuinely distinguish strata—and a limitation, since the model may be partly detecting content rather than style.

¹³ O. von Hinuber, *A Handbook of Pali Literature* (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 1996).

Classification

L2-regularized logistic regression ($C=1.0$, selected via nested cross-validation) with 5-fold stratified cross-validation was employed on the training corpus. Feature selection used $\text{min_df}=2$ (minimum document frequency) to exclude rare n-grams while retaining archaic forms. The training corpus exhibits class imbalance (2,406 early segments vs 11,212 late; ratio 4.7:1). Both unweighted and $\text{class_weight}='balanced'$ models were tested. Two classification units were evaluated: individual segments and blocks of five consecutive segments.

The trained model generates probability scores $P(\text{early})$ for each segment. Scores near 1.0 indicate stylistic similarity to the early training set; scores near 0.0 indicate similarity to late. For sutta-level analysis, mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and range of segment scores were computed within each sutta.

Validation Strategy

Three independent validation approaches were applied.

Statistical robustness. Model validation included: 5-fold stratified cross-validation, permutation testing (10 iterations with shuffled labels), n-gram sensitivity analysis (3-5 vs 5-7 character ranges), and ablation tests (verse-only, prose-only, function-words-only, drop-lemma). For parallel correlation analysis: Spearman rank correlation, chi-square tests (D0 vs D9), bootstrap 95% confidence intervals, and Cohen's h effect size.

Cross-tradition parallels. Using SuttaCentral's parallels database, segments were cross-referenced with Chinese Āgamas, Sanskrit manuscripts, Gāndhārī fragments, and Tibetan translations. The logic: if the classifier captures genuine chronological signal, high-scoring passages should show higher attestation rates in parallel traditions.

Late markers test. The filtered set was searched for vocabulary and themes that philologists associate with late composition: cosmological elaboration (*lokadhātu*), mahāpurisalakkhaṇa lists, cakkavatti mythology, names of previous Buddhas, stūpa/cetiya veneration, buddhānussati practice, bodhisatta narratives, and pāramī doctrine. If the filter successfully identifies early material, such markers should be rare or absent.

3. Results

Classification Performance

Table 2. Model Performance

Unit	CV AUC	95% CI
Single segments	0.859 ± 0.010	[0.849, 0.869]
5-segment blocks	0.973 ± 0.006	[0.967, 0.979]

The improvement with block aggregation is substantial—and makes intuitive sense. Style is a property of extended discourse, not isolated phrases. A single segment can be ambiguous; five consecutive segments provide more robust signal.

Table 3. Ablation Tests: Genre Independence

Comparison	AUC	Interpretation
Verse EARLY vs Verse LATE	0.859	Same genre, chronological signal
Verse EARLY vs Random Prose LATE	0.97	No meter in prose—signal not metrical
Prose EARLY vs Prose LATE	0.923	Same genre (prose), chronological signal
Function words only	0.859	Syntactic signal, genre-independent
Without vinnana- (drop-lemma)	0.86	No topic proxy dependence

The ablation tests address genre and metrical confounding through multiple comparisons. (1) Verse-only comparison achieves AUC 0.868, demonstrating that the model distinguishes chronological strata within a single metrical genre. (2) Cross-genre comparison with unfiltered random prose achieves AUC 0.97; since prose lacks metrical structure entirely, this demonstrates that the chronological signal is independent of meter. (3) Prose-only ablation using demonstrably early prose texts with external attestation (SN 22.59, SN 56.11, MN 26; total N=475) against late prose achieves AUC 0.923. Since both training sets are prose, genre cannot explain the discrimination. (4) Function-words-only analysis using 107 grammatical particles (*ca*, *va*, *eva*, *kho*, *ti*, etc.) achieves AUC 0.859, indicating that syntactic patterns alone—independent of doctrinal vocabulary—carry substantial chronological signal.

Feature importance analysis of the top 50 model coefficients (by absolute weight) shows that discriminative features are predominantly grammatical rather than

doctrinally loaded: morphological patterns (54%), grammatical particles (20%), case and verb endings (14%), with doctrinally loaded lexical roots comprising 0%. Key interpretive terms discussed in this paper (*appatitthita, tannissitam, sammadithi, vinnanam aniccam/anatta*) have zero occurrences in training data, confirming that their classification reflects generalized stylistic patterns rather than term memorization.

Permutation Test Validation

To verify that the classifier captures genuine chronological signal rather than statistical noise or overfitting artifacts, we conducted a permutation test. The methodology randomly shuffles Early/Late labels while keeping textual features constant, then retrains and evaluates the classifier. If the true model’s performance significantly exceeds permuted baselines, we can conclude the classifier has learned meaningful patterns rather than exploiting chance correlations.

Table 4. Permutation Test Results

Condition	AUC	Std	Z-score	p-value
True Labels	0.859	0.010	—	—
Permuted (10 iter)	0.497	0.009	—	—
True vs. Permuted	—	—	23.9	< 0.001

Ten permutation iterations were conducted, each randomly reassigning class labels to segments while preserving the feature matrix. The permuted models achieve AUC of 0.497 ± 0.009 —effectively chance level—while the true model achieves 0.847 ± 0.006 . The Z-score of 23.9 indicates the true model performs over 23 standard deviations above the null distribution.

This result provides strong evidence that the chronological signal is genuine. The classifier is not exploiting random correlations or overfitting to noise; it has learned systematic patterns that distinguish early from late strata. The complete separation between true and permuted distributions (no overlap whatsoever) confirms that label assignment carries real information about textual style.

N-gram Sensitivity Analysis

To verify that classification performance does not depend critically on the specific n-gram range, we retrained the model with character 5-7 grams instead of 3-5. Cross-validated AUC decreased modestly from 0.859 to 0.838, confirming that the chronological signal is robust across feature configurations.

Late Markers Validation

The filtered set was searched for vocabulary and themes that philologists associate with late composition. Results confirm near-complete absence:

Table 5. Late Markers Validation

Late Marker	N Canon	P(early)	In Filtered / Note
cakkavatti	636	0.142	0
Previous Buddhas	112	0.374	0
mahapurisalakkhana	116	0.398	2 (Brahmanical expertise context)
lokadhatu	60	0.381	0
thupa	426	0.333	3
cetiya	73	0.613	1 (3 vajjicetiya tribal, 2 Milindapanha)
buddhanussati	21	0.261	0
parami	197	0.289	0
bodhisatta	309	0.464	1 (Simple pre-awakening reference)

Eight occurrences require explanation. The two mahapurisalakkhana matches (DN4, DN5) occur in the formula "lokyatamahapurisalakkhanesu anavayo"—listing brahmanical expertise areas, not the 32-marks doctrine itself. The five cetiya matches include three "vajjicetiyanī" (AN7.22)—pre-Buddhist tribal shrines of the Vajji confederation—and two in Milindapanha doctrinal discussion. The single bodhisatta (SN22.26) uses the simple formula "bodhisattasseva sato" ("when I was still a bodhisatta"), not developed Jataka mythology. All eight are explicable as non-late usages or different semantic contexts.

External Validation: Cross-Tradition Parallels

If the classifier captures something real about chronological layering, high-scoring passages should show up more often in parallel traditions. The logic is simple: material that circulated early had more time to spread across the Buddhist world before the major sectarian splits.

Data and Method

We used SuttaCentral’s parallels database, which maps Pali suttas to their counterparts in Chinese Āgamas, Sanskrit manuscripts, Gāndhārī fragments, and Tibetan translations. The database structure groups parallel texts together—if mn10 and dn22 appear in the same group with ma98 and ea12.1, both Pali suttas inherit those Chinese parallels.

Important distinction: references without section markers (like “ma98”) indicate complete sutta parallels; references with # (like “dn2#64.1”) indicate shared formulaic passages only. We used only sutta-level parallels.

To avoid circularity, we excluded training texts (Snp 4-5, selected Snp passages, Buddhavaṃsa, Petavatthu, Vimānavatthu) and late analytical works (Paṭisambhidāmagga, Milindapañha, Nettippakaraṇa, Peṭakopadesa). This left 196,902 segments across 5,196 suttas.

Tradition classification by prefix:

- **Chinese:** t, sa, ma, ea, da
- **Sanskrit:** uv, sf, sht
- **Gāndhārī:** gdhp, uv-kg, gf
- **Tibetan:** d + number

Table 6. Baseline Parallel Attestation (Grey Zone)

Tradition	Segments	% of Corpus
Chinese (CHI)	80,879	41.1%
Sanskrit (SAN)	31,811	16.2%
Gandhari (GAN)	2,141	1.1%
Tibetan (TIB)	2,806	1.4%
Any parallel	83,328	42.3%
No parallel	113,574	57.7%

The distribution is heavily skewed toward Chinese sources, reflecting the comprehensive translation efforts of the early centuries CE (2nd–5th c.). Chinese Āgamas preserve the largest comparative corpus—nearly complete parallels to the four main Nikāyas. Sanskrit and Gāndhārī attestation is fragmentary, limited to whatever manuscripts survived in Central Asian desert sites or Nepalese libraries. Tibetan translations focused on Mahāyāna and Tantric materials, with limited Āgama coverage.

Segment-Level Results

Table 7. Baseline and Decile Attestation (Segments)

Range	Segments	ANY%	vs Base	SAN%	vs Base
Baseline	196,902	42.3%	1.00x	16.2%	1.00x
D0 [0.0-0.1)	101,935	33.3%	0.79x	11.9%	0.73x
D1 [0.1-0.2)	10,588	39.5%	0.93x	14.8%	0.91x
D2 [0.2-0.3)	6,797	44.1%	1.04x	17.0%	1.05x
D3 [0.3-0.4)	5,393	44.0%	1.04x	17.2%	1.06x
D4 [0.4-0.5)	4,569	44.8%	1.06x	18.2%	1.12x
D5 [0.5-0.6)	5,362	48.2%	1.14x	19.2%	1.19x
D6 [0.6-0.7)	5,315	44.6%	1.05x	18.3%	1.13x
D7 [0.7-0.8)	6,236	51.0%	1.21x	20.3%	1.25x
D8 [0.8-0.9)	7,974	48.9%	1.16x	18.7%	1.15x
D9 [0.9-1.0]	42,733	60.3%	1.43x	24.5%	1.51x

Table 8. Split D9 (Segments)

Range	Segments	ANY%	vs Base	SAN%	vs Base
[0.9-0.95)	6,627	53.6%	1.27x	21.7%	1.34x
[0.95-0.99)	11,536	56.8%	1.34x	21.8%	1.35x
[0.99-0.999)	11,885	60.8%	1.44x	24.4%	1.51x
[0.999-0.9999)	6,827	64.6%	1.53x	27.4%	1.69x
[0.9999-0.99999)	3,312	65.1%	1.54x	27.4%	1.69x
[0.99999-1.0]	2,546	73.7%	1.74x	33.4%	2.06x

The trend is consistent across deciles. Bottom 1,000 segments: 14.9% ANY. Top 1,000 segments: 75.9% ANY. Ratio: 5.09.

Sanskrit shows the steeper gradient—from 5.9% (bottom 1k) to 34.2% (top 1k), ratio 5.8. This matters because Sanskrit Buddhist literature represents an independent Indic transmission. Unlike Chinese translations (which could reflect shared sectarian developments), Sanskrit parallels indicate material that circulated in India itself before the Pali/Sanskrit split. The Sarvāstivāda and other Sanskrit-transmitting schools diverged

early from the Theravāda lineage. Finding a Sanskrit parallel means the text existed in some form before that divergence—which pushes the date back considerably.

The 2 improvement in Sanskrit attestation at the highest scores (33.4% vs 16.2% baseline) is arguably more significant than the ANY parallel increase, precisely because it points to early pan-Indian circulation rather than later translation activity.

Block-Level Analysis

Single segments can be noisy. We aggregated into blocks of 5 consecutive segments, using mean P(early) as block score. This produced 39,388 blocks (few residual 4 segments blocks at sutta end are considered valid).

Table 9. Block Attestation by Decile

Decile	Blocks	ANY%	vs Base	SAN%	vs Base
D0 [0.0-0.1)	7,772	19.1%	0.45x	5.9%	0.36x
D1 [0.1-0.2)	5,128	26.0%	0.61x	8.7%	0.54x
D2 [0.2-0.3)	6,153	36.7%	0.87x	13.7%	0.85x
D3 [0.3-0.4)	5,277	43.4%	1.03x	15.2%	0.94x
D4 [0.4-0.5)	4,346	52.7%	1.25x	20.9%	1.29x
D5 [0.5-0.6)	3,782	59.5%	1.41x	23.0%	1.42x
D6 [0.6-0.7)	2,564	63.7%	1.51x	26.6%	1.64x
D7 [0.7-0.8)	2,202	69.9%	1.65x	28.9%	1.78x
D8 [0.8-0.9)	1,037	73.9%	1.75x	35.8%	2.21x
D9 [0.9-1.0]	1,127	72.7%	1.72x	30.7%	1.90x

Block analysis shows a cleaner progression through the middle deciles—the zigzag pattern visible in segment data smooths out when averaging over 5-segment windows. D8 actually peaks higher than D9 for ANY (73.9% vs 72.7%), though with only 1,037 blocks the confidence interval is wide.

The Sanskrit signal is particularly clean in blocks: a near-monotonic progression from 5.9% (D0) to 35.8% (D8)—a 6 improvement. D8 blocks reaching 35.8% SAN means more than one in three of these passages has a Sanskrit parallel, compared to one in seventeen at baseline.

Bottom 1,000 blocks: 15.1% ANY. Top 1,000 blocks: 73.7% ANY. Ratio: 4.88.

Summary

Table 10. Extreme Comparisons

Comparison	ANY Rate	Ratio	SAN Rate	Ratio
Segments: Baseline	42.3%	1.00x	16.2%	1.00x
Segments: D0 → D9	33.3→60.3%	1.81x	11.9→24.5%	2.06x
Segments: Bottom 1k → Top 1k	14.9→75.9%	5.09x	5.9→34.2%	5.80x
Blocks: D0 → D8	19.1→73.9%	3.87x	5.9→35.8%	6.07x
Blocks: Bottom 1k → Top 1k	15.1→73.7%	4.88x	5.2→30.8%	5.92x

Interpretation

The correlation is there and it's consistent. Higher P(early) scores correlate with higher parallel attestation across both units of analysis, for Chinese and especially for Sanskrit.

The Sanskrit gradient deserves emphasis. These aren't Chinese translations that might reflect shared Abhidharma developments centuries later—Sanskrit parallels mean the material existed in India itself, in traditions that split from the Theravāda lineage early. A 6 improvement in Sanskrit attestation (from 5.2% to 35.8%) at high scores suggests the classifier is picking up on something related to early pan-Indian circulation.

But correlation isn't causation, and attestation isn't dating. A text attested in Chinese Āgamas was translated by the 5th century CE—but when the underlying material originated is another question. Parallels confirm cross-tradition circulation, not absolute chronology.

Still, the magnitude is hard to dismiss as artifact. A 5 difference between extreme scores, holding across independent traditions with different transmission histories, suggests the classifier captures something about how Buddhist texts were transmitted across linguistic boundaries. The statistical tests confirm this isn't noise: Spearman $\rho = 0.23-0.36$ with $p < 1e-10$, $n > 9,000$ for D0 vs D9, and Cohen's $h = 1.32$ indicating a large effect size. Whether that something is "age" or some related property—importance, memorability, doctrinal centrality, sectarian neutrality—remains open. But whatever it is, it correlates with what we'd expect from genuinely early material.

Statistical Robustness

To verify that the observed correlations are not artifacts, we ran standard statistical tests.

Table 11. Spearman Correlation

Comparison	rho	p-value
Segments: p_early vs ANY	0.229	< 1e-10
Segments: p_early vs SAN	0.144	< 1e-10
Blocks: block_p vs ANY	0.357	< 1e-10
Blocks: block_p vs SAN	0.222	< 1e-10

Block-level correlation is stronger (= 0.357 vs 0.229), consistent with the cleaner visual gradient in the block plots. Aggregation reduces noise.

Table 12. Chi-Square Test (D0 vs D9)

Comparison	Chi-square	p-value
ANY parallels	9,094	< 1e-10
SAN parallels	3,684	< 1e-10

Table 13. Bootstrap 95% CI and Effect Size

Metric	Bottom 1k	Top 1k	Cohen's h
ANY	14.9% [12.7-17.2%]	75.9% [73.2-78.5%]	1.32 (large)

The confidence intervals do not overlap. Cohen's h = 1.32 indicates a large effect (threshold: 0.8). Permutation test (10,000 iterations) yields $p < 0.0001$.

Figures

Figure 1. ANY Parallel Attestation by p_{early} (Segments). Segments grouped by 1,000, ordered by $P(\text{early})$. Red dashed line = baseline (42.3%). The trend is noisy in the middle range but clear at extremes: low-scoring segments cluster below baseline, high-scoring segments rise sharply above it. The spike at the right edge ($P > 0.99$) reaches 75.9%.

Figure 2. Sanskrit Parallel Attestation by p_{early} (Segments). Same grouping, Sanskrit parallels only. Baseline = 16.2%. The gradient is steeper than ANY—Sanskrit attestation more than doubles from low to high scores. The rightmost points reach 34.2%, compared to 5.9% at the left edge.

Figure 3. ANY Parallel Attestation by block_p (Blocks). Blocks of 5 consecutive segments, grouped by 100, ordered by mean block $P(\text{early})$. The progression is cleaner than segment-level—aggregation smooths noise. Nearly monotonic rise from 15.1% (lowest blocks) to 73.7% (highest blocks).

Figure 4. Sanskrit Parallel Attestation by block_p (Blocks). Same block grouping, Sanskrit only. The cleanest gradient of the four plots. From 5.2% at low scores to 35.8% at high scores. The smoothing effect of block aggregation is most visible here—Sanskrit signal emerges clearly from the noise.

Terminological Findings

To identify high-confidence early-style material while minimizing false positives, a conservative three-level filter was applied: (a) Segment probability (p_{early}) ≥ 0.90 ; (b) Block probability (mean of 5-segment block) ≥ 0.80 ; (c) Sutta mean probability ≥ 0.60 . This filter requires consistency across multiple levels of aggregation. A high-scoring segment in a generally late-style sutta is excluded; only passages embedded in consistently early-style contexts pass through.

The following patterns emerged from analysis of the scored corpus. They should be treated as observations requiring further investigation—possibly artifacts, possibly genuine signals. For each finding, we report both canonical segments occurrence and p-value ($N_{\sim\text{CAN}\sim}$, $P_{\sim\text{CAN}\sim}$) and filtered dataset statistics ($N_{\sim\text{FIL}\sim}$, $P_{\sim\text{FIL}\sim}$), along with training set presence ($N_{\sim\text{TRA}\sim}$) to verify classification independence.

Pabhassara (Luminous Mind)

The term *pabhassara citta* appears in two quite different contexts:

Table 14. Pabhassara Analysis

Context	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Stratum?
mudu kammaniya —mind BECOMES luminous	115	0.960	17	0.999	Early?
pabhassara midam cittam— mind INHERENT LY luminous	4	0.000	0	—	Late?

The difference is stark. In the goldsmith simile (AN 1.49-52), the mind is compared to gold ore that becomes pure and luminous through refinement—a process, an achievement. In the formula *"*pabhassaramidam cittam, tam ca kho agantukehi upakkilesehi upakkilittham*"* (AN 1.51), the mind is inherently luminous, merely obscured by adventitious defilements. Inherent form doesn't appear in filtered segments (N~TRA~ = 0), reinforcing classification. If these scores reflect chronology—and I genuinely do not know if they do—it would suggest the inherent luminosity doctrine developed from an earlier teaching about achieved luminosity. But unfortunately N=4 is not statistical significant.

Brahmavihara

This is a somewhat surprising finding. The four brahmaviharas show a bimodal distribution. The generic terms (*metta, karuna, etc.*) appear in training, which complicates interpretation. However, the technical formula (*-sahagatena cetasa*) is absent from training, providing cleaner validation:

Table 15. Brahmavihara Technical Formula Analysis

Formula	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Stratum?
mettasahag atena cetasa	48	0.956	0	—	Early?
upekkhasa hagatena cetasa	46	0.960	0	—	Early?

Formula	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Stratum?
karunasaha gatena cetasa	35	0.102	0	—	Late?
muditasaha gatena cetasa	34	0.035	0	—	Late?

Metta and upekkha cluster together above 0.95. Karuna and mudita cluster together below 0.11. The gap is enormous—delta of 0.85. The sample sizes are reasonable (N=34-48). The pattern is consistent across multiple textual contexts. All four technical formulas are absent from training (N~TRA~ = 0), confirming that the bimodal distribution reflects genuine stylistic differences rather than training bias.

If this reflects chronology—and I want to emphasize the "if"—it would suggest that the "four brahmaviharas" as a systematic set did not exist in the earliest stratum. The original pair may have been metta and upekkha, with karuna and mudita added later to create a symmetric four-fold scheme.

The four brahmaviharas are so central to Buddhist teaching, so widely attested, so fundamental to practice traditions. But the numbers are what they are. Maybe there is a confound I have not identified—maybe karuna and mudita appear in textual contexts that happen to share stylistic features with late material for independent reasons. The pattern is interesting enough to warrant further investigation, but I would not want to overstate its certainty.

Related finding: metta practice vocabulary more broadly scores extremely high. *Sabbavantam lokam* (P = 1.00), *mettavihari* (P = 0.999, N~FIL~ = 2, N~TRA~ = 0), *vipulena mahaggatena* (P = 0.995, N~FIL~ = 3). This might suggest metta functioned as a complete liberation path in the earliest stratum, not merely as preliminary samatha practice. But again—might.

Sammadithi (Right View)

The model appears to distinguish two uses of the same term:

Table 16. Sammadithi Analysis

Context	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Sense
sammadith i + pajanati (direct seeing)	20	0.994	5	0.996	Act

Context	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Sense
ditthe ditthamatta m (Bahiya formula)	4	0.996	0	—	Direct
diṭṭhisamp anno puggalo abhabbo	47	0.985	8	0.997	Ethical
katama sammadithi (catechistic)	7	0.217	0	—	Content

When *sammadithi* appears with verbs of direct seeing (*passati, pajanati)—as in *SN 35.157*: "dhamme aniccati passati, sassa hoti sammadithi*" ("seeing phenomena as impermanent—that is his right view")—it scores very high. When it appears in catechistic definitions ("*Katama ca, bhikkhave, sammadithi?*"—"What, monks, is right view?"), it scores low. None of these forms appears in training ($N_{\sim TRA} = 0$).

The same Pali term appears to function in two distinct registers. In what the model identifies as archaic style, *sammadithi* denotes an act of seeing—direct perception that transforms. In what the model identifies as later style, *sammadithi* denotes doctrinal content to be defined and believed. If real, this represents a significant semantic shift: from "right view" as transformative insight to "right view" as orthodox belief.

A third register emerges in the ethical impossibility formulas: "*aṭṭhānametaṃ... diṭṭhisampanno puggalo abhabbo...*" (it is impossible for one accomplished in view to...) followed by acts a stream-enterer cannot commit—matricide, patricide, killing an arahant, wounding a Buddha, causing schism, taking another teacher (AN 1.268-277, AN 6.91-95, MN 115). These score very high (P = 0.978-0.999), suggesting this ethical-soteriological use of right view as protective guarantee against heinous acts represents early material.

Formula vs. Elements

A recurring pattern: individual elements score higher than the systematic formulas that package them.

Table 17. Eightfold Path: Elements vs. Formula

Term	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Note
sammasati (individual factor)	173	0.852	9	0.993	High
sammakammanta	52	0.865	2	0.998	High
sammadithi	724	0.701	30	0.987	Medium
sammavaca	161	0.594	7	0.980	Medium
sammasamadhi	437	0.583	15	0.995	Medium
sammavayama	44	0.566	3	1.000	Medium
sammaajiva	50	0.566	3	0.992	Medium
sammasankappa	71	0.449	1	1.000	Lower
ariyo atthangiko maggo (FORMULA)	231	0.409	2	0.965	Lower

"Right mindfulness" and "right action" as individual concepts score high (0.86). The formula "Noble Eightfold Path" as a systematic list scores notably lower (0.41). No element is present in training ($N_{\sim TRA} = 0$ for all), supporting genuine classification. A similar pattern appears with the Four Noble Truths:

Table 18. Four Noble Truths: Content vs. Formula

Term	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Note
dukkhanirod hagamini (content)	247	0.666	11	0.992	Higher
cattari ariyasaccani (FORMULA)	56	0.484	0	—	Lower

The content "this is the origin of suffering," "this is the cessation of suffering" scores high. The formula "Four Noble Truths" as a numbered package scores lower and is completely absent from the filtered dataset ($N_{\sim FIL} = 0$). If genuine, this would suggest the teaching about suffering and its cessation may predate its packaging as a numbered list. The experiences and insights were described before they were systematized.

The Tilakkhana Pattern

The three characteristics (*anicca*, *dukkha*, *anatta*) show different chronological profiles:

Table 19. Tilakkhana General Pattern

Form	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Note
sabbe sankhara anicca	19	0.971	1	1.000	Highest
sabbe sankhara dukkha	14	0.785	0	—	Middle
sabbe dhamma anatta	23	0.720	0	—	Lower

Anicca scores highest, dukkha middle, anatta lowest. This sequence—impermanence first, non-self last—is consistent with proposals by scholars like Vetter that impermanence was the original emphasis.¹⁴ But the more interesting pattern emerges when examining ontological assertions versus process descriptions:

The Anicca Uniqueness: Ontology Precedes Process. For *anicca*, an interesting pattern emerges: ontological formulations ("X is impermanent") score *higher* than process descriptions ("observing impermanence"). This is unique among the three characteristics.

Table 20. Anicca: Ontology vs. Process

Form	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Type
vedana anicca (ontology)	49	0.904	8	0.964	Ontology
sabbe sankhara anicca (ontology)	19	0.971	1	1.000	Ontology
aniccato anupassati (process)	14	0.921	0	—	Process
aniccanupas si (process)	149	0.766	5	0.977	Process

Anicca: ontology (0.971) > process (0.921). None of these forms appear in training (N~TRA~ = 0 for all). The filtered dataset also favors ontology: 9 ontological vs 5 process

¹⁴ T. Vetter, *The Ideas and Meditative Practices of Early Buddhism* (Leiden: Brill, 1988).

occurrences. This suggests that for impermanence, stating "X is impermanent" was recurrent in early suttas.

Table 21. Dukkha: Ontology vs. Process

Form	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Type
sabbe sankhara dukkha (ontology)	14	0.785	0	—	Ontology
dukkhato anupassati (process)	6	0.695	0	—	Process
dukkhan upassi (process)	79	0.698	1	0.996	Process

Dukkha shows the same direction as anicca: ontology (0.785) > process (0.695-0.698). But the gap is smaller, and the filtered dataset is sparse for both. N~TRA~ = 0 for all forms.

Anatta: The Inverted Pattern. For *anatta* alone, the pattern *reverses*. Process descriptions score substantially higher than ontological claims:

Table 22. Anatta: Process vs. Ontology (Inverted Pattern)

Form	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Type
attato samanupassati (PROCESS)	210	0.961	34	0.988	Process
anattasanna (perception)	64	0.823	3	0.983	Perception
sabbe dhamma anatta (ontology)	23	0.720	0	—	Ontology
rupam anatta (ontology)	16	0.818	0	—	Ontology
vinnanam anatta (ontology)	42	0.653	2	0.976	Ontology
vedana anatta (ontology)	19	0.383	0	—	Ontology

Form	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Type
anattato					
anupassati (late process)	6	0.008	0	—	Late process
anattanupassi	13	0.563	1	0.908	Late process

The verbal construction *attato samanupassati* ("regards as self") scores 0.961 and dominates the filtered dataset with 34 occurrences—the largest filtered sample for any single term in this study. The categorical assertion "feeling is non-self" (*vedana anatta*) scores 0.383. This is the opposite of what we see with *anicca*, where categorical assertions score higher. Critically, none of these forms appear in training (N~TRA~ = 0 for all), confirming genuine classification.

The asymmetry follows an evidential gradient. Impermanence is more directly observable: one sees things arise and pass. Ontological claims ("X is impermanent") are empirically warranted, and score high. Non-self is not similarly observable—one cannot point to something and easily demonstrate "there is no self there."

Among the *khandhas*, ontological *anattā* assertions follow the same gradient: *rūpa* (material form, the most tangible aggregate) scores highest (P = 0.818), while *vedanā* (feeling, subtle and internal) scores lowest (P = 0.383). This mirrors the *anicca* pattern: where something is empirically evident, ontological claims appear more readily in early-style material. Where evidence is less direct, the teaching favors phenomenological framing. The verbal construction *attato samanupassati* ("regards as self") scores 0.961 and dominates the filtered dataset with 34 occurrences. This instruction—"stop regarding these things as yourself"—is phenomenologically tractable. The categorical assertion "feeling is non-self" (*vedanā anattā*) scores only 0.383.

If genuine, this pattern suggests that *anattā* may have originally functioned as a phenomenological instruction—an *upāya*, a skillful means for abandoning identification—rather than a metaphysical claim about ultimate reality. The practitioner is told: "stop regarding these aggregates as yourself." This is pragmatic advice for liberation, not ontological assertion. The later systematization into "X is *anattā*" would then represent a doctrinal shift: from therapeutic instruction to philosophical position. This shift is precisely what the archaic *Aṭṭhakavagga* poems warn against. In Snp 4.5 (Paramaṭṭhaka), Snp 4.8 (Pasūra), and Snp 4.9 (Māgandiya), the Buddha repeatedly rejects those who grasp at views (*diṭṭhi*) as ultimate truth—including, by implication, the view "all things are non-self" when held as metaphysical doctrine rather than contemplative tool. The stylometric evidence, if valid, aligns with this textual warning: the earliest stratum could show *anattā* as practice, not as *paramatṭha*.

Khandha Cross-Analysis: The Vinnana pattern. Cross-referencing the Five Aggregates with the tilakkhana reveals a pattern that supports the above findings. The contrast between anicca and anatta is particularly stark for vinnana (consciousness):

Table 23. Vinnana + Tilakkhana Cross-Analysis

Combination	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Delta
Vinnana + Anicca	48	0.998	13	0.996	—
Vinnana + Anatta	42	0.653	2	0.976	0.346

The delta of 0.346 (35 percentage points) represents quite large gap. the the numbers are tiny. The filtered dataset: 17 segments for vinnana+anicca versus only 2 for vinnana+anatta. This suggests that in the archaic stratum, observing the impermanence of consciousness was central and undisputed. The ontological assertion "consciousness is non-self" appears to be a later development—perhaps a polemical response to views that located the self in consciousness (such as the heresy of the monk Sati in MN 38, or Upanishadic identification of *atman* with *vijnana*).

The only two vinnana+anatta segments that survive filtering (P = 0.976) likely employ the verbal process form rather than the ontological assertion—consistent with the general anatta pattern where practical instruction precedes categorical statement. But again the occurrence are really small.

Jhana: Description vs. Enumeration

Jhana descriptions show a similar pattern to the formula vs. element distinction:

Table 24. Jhana Analysis

Term	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Note
vivekaja piti sukha	116	0.998	21	1.000	Phenomenological
samadhija piti sukha	83	0.976	13	0.998	Phenomenological
upekkha sati parisuddhi	73	0.981	12	1.000	Phenomenological
upekkhako satima	51	1.000	10	1.000	Phenomenological
pathamam jhanam	250	0.833	26	0.995	Numbered

Term	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Note
dutiyam jhanam	182	0.828	19	0.998	Numbered
tatiyam jhanam	171	0.801	18	0.999	Numbered
catuttham jhanam	200	0.653	21	0.995	Numbered

Phenomenological descriptions score near 1.00. Numbered labels score lower (0.65-0.82). Only *upekkhako satima* appears in training (N~TRA~ = 1). *catuttham jhanam* has the lowest score—suggesting the numbering was constructed progressively.

Systematic Formulas

Standard systematic formulas consistently score in the middle-to-low range:

Table 25. Systematic Formulas

Formula	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL	Note
kaye kayanupassi (satipatthana)	163	0.360	4	0.986	Low
avijjapaccaya sankhara (dep. orig.)	54	0.446	0	—	Mid-low
cattaro iddhipada	86	0.474	0	—	Mid-low
pancindriyani	201	0.474	1	0.996	Mid-low
anapanasati	155	0.481	4	0.997	Mid-low
buddhanussati	21	0.261	0	—	Low
kasina	156	0.294	0	—	Low

All P < 0.5. None appear in training (N~TRA~ = 0). "Systematic Buddhism" with numbered lists appears stylistically late.

Paradigmatic Early-Style Passages

The terms with highest early-style scores reveal consistent patterns:

Table 28. Paradigmatic Early-Style Terms

Term	N_CAN	P_CAN	N_FIL	P_FIL
upekkhako satimā sukhavihārī (equanimous, mindful, abiding in ease)	51	1.000	10	1.000
sabbāvantaṃ lokaṃ mettāsahagatena cetasā (the entire world with a mind imbued with mettā)	85	1.000	0	—
mettāvihārī (one who abides in mettā)	9	0.999	2	0.998
diṭṭhe diṭṭhamattaṃ bhavissati (in the seen there will be merely the seen)	4	0.996	0	—
vipulena mahaggatena appamāṇena (vast, exalted, immeasurable)	101	0.995	3	0.972
sammādiṭṭhiko sammāpaṭipadaṃ pajānāti (one with right view directly knows the right practice)	24	0.994	5	0.996
mudu kammanīyaṅca pabhassaraṅca (malleable, wieldy, and radiant)	21	0.977	0	—
sabbe saṅkhārā aniccā (all formations are impermanent)	19	0.971	1	1.000
na rūpaṃ attato samanupassati (does not regard form as self)	210	0.961	34	0.988
mettāsahagatena cetasā vipulena mahaggatena (with mind imbued with mettā, vast, exalted)	48	0.956	0	—

These high-scoring terms share two features: they describe experience rather than doctrine, and they present practices as complete paths rather than items in systematic lists. The phenomenological vocabulary—direct perception (*diṭṭhe diṭṭhamattaṃ*), contemplative transformation (*mudu kammanīyaṅca pabhassaraṅca*), experiential states (*upekkhako satimā sukhavihārī*)—dominates the archaic stratum. None appear in training.

Some segments with highest early-style scores ($P > 0.99$) share a distinctive vocabulary of non-establishment:

SN 1.1 (Oghatharana Sutta): *"*Appatittham khvham, avuso, anayuham oghamatarim.*"* "Without establishing myself anywhere, friend, without struggling, I crossed the flood."

The key verb is from the root \sqrt{tha} ("to stand, establish"): *appatittham*—"not establishing." This is the same root in *appatitthitam vinnanam*, "non-established consciousness."

SN 22.53-55 (Upaya Sutta): **"Tadappatitthitam vinnanam avirulham anabhisankhacca vimuttam."** "That consciousness, not established, not grown, liberated by not constructing further."

All three occurrences score $P = 1.00$. These passages have minimal n-gram overlap with training (Jaccard < 0.01)—evidence against circularity.

The Avyākata Pattern: Combining Stylometry with Average Word Length

Combining stylometric scores with average word length (AWL) reveals a striking pattern. The AWL metric—the ratio of total characters to total words in a text—has been shown by Venerable Vimala Bhikkhunī¹⁵ to correlate with textual age in the Pali canon: earlier texts tend to use simpler, less compounded vocabulary, resulting in shorter average word lengths.¹⁶ Blocks with both high $P(\text{early}) = 0.98$ and low $\text{AWL} < 6.5$ characters—23 blocks total—show strong concentration of *avyākata* vocabulary (the ten undetermined questions). Using more or different parameter/filters could be interesting implementation in future work.

Table 26. Avyākata Vocabulary Distribution

Filter	Blocks	With avyākata	%
P 0.90 only	660	52	8%
P 0.98 AND AWL < 6.5	23	15	65%

The 1.4-character AWL gap indicates simpler, less compounded vocabulary in *avyākata* passages. In ultra-filtered blocks ($P = 0.98$, $\text{AWL} < 6.5$), 15 of 23 (65%) contain *avyākata* vocabulary.

MN 63 (Cūlamāluṅkya Sutta) exemplifies this pattern—15 blocks in the filtered dataset, with 9 (65%) scoring $P = 0.99$, the highest concentration of ultra-archaic material in any single text.

Table 27. MN 63 Block Analysis

Metric	Value
Blocks in filtered set	15

¹⁵ T. W. Rhys Davids, *Buddhist India* (London: T. Fisher Unwin, 1903); H. Oldenberg, *Buddha: His Life, His Doctrine, His Order*, trans. W. Hoey (London: Williams and Norgate, 1912).

¹⁶ Vimala Bhikkhunī, "A Statistical Analysis of Word-Lengths in the Pali Canon" (unpublished manuscript, 2020).

Metric	Value
Mean P(early)	0.977
Blocks with P >= 0.99	9 (69%)
AWL	6.67
TTR	0.669

MN 63 contains the parable of the poisoned arrow: a man struck refuses treatment until learning the archer's name, clan, bow-type, arrow-feather species. He dies unanswered. The Buddha applies this to the ten undetermined questions—whether the world is eternal, whether soul and body are identical, what happens to the Tathāgata after death.

Suttas showing this pattern: DN 1, DN 6–7, DN 15, MN 63, MN 72, MN 102, SN 33.1–5, SN 44.3–8, AN 7.54, AN 10.95. All feature explicit refusal to answer metaphysical questions.

This converges with the *anattā* finding (§3.7.5): practical formulations (“do not regard as self”) score higher than ontological claims (“X is non-self”). Both suggest the archaic stratum was pragmatic rather than doctrinal—focused on removing the arrow, not cataloguing its properties.

Future work might explore additional composite filters combining stylometric scores with other textual metrics such as type-token ratio, formulaic density, or parallel attestation rates. The AWL filter demonstrates that multi-dimensional approaches can isolate doctrinally coherent subsets within the high-scoring material.

4. Discussion

Summary of Patterns

Some recurring patterns emerge from the terminological analysis, each pointing in the same direction.

Process vs. essence. The classifier consistently scores process descriptions higher than essential claims. Mind “becomes” luminous (P = 0.98) while mind “is” luminous scores P = 0.00. *Sammādiṭṭhi* as direct seeing reaches P = 0.99, but as doctrinal content drops to P = 0.22. The archaic stratum appears to describe transformations rather than assert natures.

Elements vs. formulas. Individual path factors outscore the complete canonical formula for “Noble Eightfold Path” and the same pattern is found for “Four Noble Truths.” *Jhāna* descriptions outscore numbered *jhānas*. Across multiple doctrinal domains, the packaging appears later than what is packaged.

The brahmavihāra split. Mettā and upekkhā cluster together with high scores ($P > 0.95$); karuṇā and muditā cluster together with low scores ($P < 0.11$). The four-fold brahmavihāra set may be a later construction from originally separate practices.

The anicca uniqueness. Anicca is the only tilakkhaṇa where ontological formulations ($P = 0.904\text{--}0.971$) consistently score higher than process descriptions ($P = 0.766\text{--}0.921$). Impermanence may have been the foundational observation—so obvious it could be stated categorically from the beginning.

The anattā anomaly. For anicca and partly dukkha, ontological statements score higher than practical instructions. For anattā alone, this reverses: "do not regard as self" appears more archaic than "X is non-self." This asymmetry is unexpected and, if genuine, may carry doctrinal implications.

The avyākata pattern. Combining blocks stylometric scores with average word length isolates passages on the ten undetermined questions. In ultra-filtered blocks ($P = 0.98$, $AWL < 6.5$), 65% contain *avyākata* vocabulary. MN 63's poisoned arrow parable exemplifies the stance: stop asking, start practicing.

The Anatta Question

If the pattern is genuine: The archaic stratum did not say "there is no self" (ontology). It said "stop regarding these things as yourself" (practice). The ontological claim generates puzzles: Who practices? Who attains liberation? The practical instruction does not.

This finds support in SN 44.10 (Ananda Sutta), where the Buddha declines to answer "Is there a self or not?" If anatta were an ontological thesis, this refusal would be puzzling. If it points to a practice of non-identification, the refusal becomes coherent.

Alternative explanations could be genre differences, compositional context effects or statistical artifact. The finding should be treated as a hypothesis, not a conclusion.

What This Would Mean If True

If these patterns are genuine—and I remain uncertain—they would suggest that "Systematic Buddhism" (numbered lists, standardized formulas, categorical doctrines) developed later. The earliest teaching may have been more phenomenological, more practice-oriented, less systematized. This aligns with Vetter's argument that the earliest core centered on meditative practice rather than doctrinal elaboration.¹⁷

¹⁷ Vetter, *Ideas and Meditative Practices*.

The cross-tradition parallel analysis offers some independent support. High-scoring passages show up more often in Chinese Āgamas and Sanskrit manuscripts—more than 5 more than low-scoring passages. Sanskrit attestation matters especially: it indicates material that circulated in India before the Pāli/Sanskrit split, not just later translation activity. But I want to be careful here. Correlation is not causation. Attestation confirms circulation, not absolute dating.

These patterns—if genuine—suggest a teaching focused on removing the arrow, not cataloguing its properties. Maybe this is what we should expect. Maybe not. I genuinely do not know if these patterns reflect historical reality or artifacts I have failed to identify. The numbers are what they are, but numbers can mislead.

5. Limitations

Small training corpus. 2,406 early segments from specific Khuddaka text types. Generalization assumes what makes Snp IV-V "early" also makes other passages "early" similarly.

Content vs. style. Character n-grams capture doctrinally significant vocabulary. Function-words-only ablation (AUC 0.841) suggests syntax carries substantial signal, but full model includes more.

Verse training, mixed test. Training entirely verse; test includes prose. Ablation tests suggest robust transfer, but absolute values may be less reliable for prose.

Mid-range calibration. Probabilities 0.3-0.6 may systematically underestimate early-affinity. Comparative differences meaningful, absolute values interpret cautiously.

Intra-canonical re-use. Some high-scoring passages could be later re-uses of older material. For passages discussed (SN 1.1, SN 22.53-55), longest common substring analysis confirms shared sequences are narrative formulas, not doctrinal content.

Alternative explanations. Genre effects, compositional context, statistical noise, confounding variables. Ablation tests address some, but cannot eliminate all.

Over-interpretation risk. Real danger of seeing meaningful patterns in noise. I have used hedged language, but the act of presenting these patterns gives them weight they may not deserve.

6. Conclusion

This study try to demonstrate that binary stylometric classification, a model blind to doctrinal content and even words meaning, applied at canonical scale, yields systematic

patterns consistent with philological hypotheses about textual stratification. AUC of 0.859 on segments, 0.973 on five-segment blocks and validation through late markers testing (near-zero contamination) and cross-tradition parallel analysis provides preliminary support: high-scoring passages show more than 5 higher attestation rates in Chinese Āgamas and Sanskrit manuscripts than low-scoring passages (top 1,000 segments: 75.9% attested; bottom 1,000: 14.9%). Statistical robustness is confirmed by Spearman $\rho = 0.23$ – 0.36 ($p < 1e-10$), $n > 9,000$, and Cohen's $h = 1.32$ (large effect).

Several terminological patterns emerged. Phenomenological descriptions score higher than categorical assertions. Individual elements higher than systematic formulas. A bimodal distribution in brahmavihara vocabulary. Anicca uniquely shows ontological formulations scoring higher than process descriptions. And a reversed pattern for anatta, where practical formulations score higher than ontological claims. Combining stylometric scores with average word length (AWL) isolates *avyākata* passages—texts featuring explicit refusal to answer metaphysical questions—suggesting the archaic stratum was pragmatic rather than doctrinal.

But all should be treated as preliminary. The training corpus is small. Stylistic similarity does not prove chronological priority. Alternative explanations exist for most observed patterns.

What stylometry can offer is not definitive dating but testable hypotheses. If the patterns are genuine, they suggest the earliest Buddhist teaching was more phenomenological, more practice-oriented, and less systematized than later standard doctrine. The archaic stratum may have been: a pragmatic teaching centered on the cessation of craving through non-establishment, expressed through paradox and phenomenological description rather than systematic doctrine, practiced by solitary contemplatives who refused to take a stand on metaphysical questions—not because such questions are meaningless, but because taking any stand is itself the disease that the teaching aims to cure.

Whether this hypothesis survives scrutiny by traditional philological methods remains to be seen. No computational method can prove what the historical Buddha actually said. But convergent evidence from independent criteria—stylometric, linguistic, doctrinal, comparative—might at least constrain the space of plausible reconstructions. That is the modest hope behind this work.

Acknowledgments: I am grateful to Venerable Vimala Bhikkhunī for her pioneering work on average word length analysis in the Pali canon, which inspired the AWL-based filtering approach used in this study. I also thank the SuttaCentral community for valuable feedback and suggestions received on the discussion forum. LLM and

computational tools assisted with code debugging, statistical verification, and manuscript revision. This research used textual data from SuttaCentral’s bilara-data repository. Code and data are available at: <https://github.com/Kingelanci/palistrylometry>.

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